

PREPSOIL DELIVERABLE

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V3	21.05.2025	L. Malmquist	Addition of references & annex
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Summary

This report synthesises the results from a questionnaire within the project PREPSOIL – Preparing for the ‘Soil Deal for Europe’ Mission, Task 5.2. Earth Observation techniques for Soil Health monitoring. This report aimed to identify opportunities and challenges for the use of remote sensing in soil monitoring to inform action in enhancing soil health in Sweden. The survey was aimed towards experts in organisations, companies, authorities and research institutes with knowledge of remote sensing, GIS, soil health and environmental analysis within the farming sector, forest sector and urban areas. The survey was active between 2025-03-20 and 2025-05-25. In total, 13 questionnaires were completed (of total 33 individuals invited) mainly active within the agricultural sectors.

The main results where:

- There was a general optimism for remote sensing data and applications in soil health monitoring with potential to improve resolution and reduce (data and analyses) cost.
- Stronger collaboration and improved communication between data providers, researchers and end-users, supported by training opportunities, could facilitate increased use of remote sensing.
- There was an identified need for harmonised validation and error quantification as well as standardised platforms for access of data to end-users.
- The existing national soil monitoring data is seen as a reliable source for assessing soil health, while remote sensing data was seen as a potential complement. However, current capacity to enhance soil health monitoring with assistance of remote sensing was still viewed as limited.

I. Introduction

This report synthesises the results from a questionnaire within the project PREPSOIL – *Preparing for the ‘Soil Deal for Europe’ Mission, Task 5.2. Earth Observation techniques for Soil Health monitoring*. Remote sensing products offer opportunities for large-scale continuous and cost-effective soil monitoring. However, despite the increasing maturity and technological development of remote sensing tools, their practical use in soil monitoring remains challenging. Expert statements from France, Poland, Norway and Czech Republic show challenges such as lack of expertise amongst end-users and local authorities for interpreting and applying remote sensing data, limited availability of harmonised datasets and high-resolution remote sensing products, incompatibility of spatial and temporal scales, physical obstacles for optical sensors and difficulties in standardized data processing. Lastly, engagement and training from stakeholders can be limiting the full potential of remote sensing data (Renault et al., 2024).

Soil monitoring in Sweden is organised through the soil and crop inventory for agricultural soils (Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet, 2022) and for forest through the Swedish forest soil inventory (Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, 2023). Urban environment is on the other hand covered by monitoring by multiple localized stakeholders, while partly coordinated through collaborative networks, (e.g. Nätverket Renare mark, <https://www.renaremark.se/>).

The aim with this report was to identify opportunities and challenges to promote the use of remote sensing to enhance soil health in a Swedish context. Secondly, the questionnaire sought to propose measures to minimise potential challenges for the application and use of remote sensing for continued work on soil health within the EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe, from a perspective from Swedish experts.

II. Methods

A questionnaire comprising of 19 main questions (Annex I: Questionnaire) concerning the usage, opportunities and challenges of using remote sensing to monitor soil health in Sweden, was shared with selected authorities and organisations (Table 1) during March and April, 2025, with complementary requests for participation sent to selected respondents. The questions were formulated as multiple-choice questions. The suggested choices were formulated based on answers from workshops previously held in Poland, the Czech Republic, Norway, and France within PREPSOIL WP5-Task 5.2.

The invitation to respondents for participation was sent out via email. The questionnaire was shared via the online platform Netigate (<https://www.netigate.net/>). Key individuals with potential knowledge in GIS, remote sensing, soil health, environmental analysis within the farming sector, forest sector and/or urban sectors were contacted. In total, 33 individuals were contacted directly to answer the questionnaire. In addition, an unknown number of people received the questionnaire forwarded from colleagues. A reminder was sent to persons not responding, and complementing contacts were made in the beginning of May.

Table 1. Contacted organisations, companies and authorities for survey in Sweden

Category	Number of contacted businesses	Number of contacted respondents
Authority	7	15
Private sector	7	14
Research institutes	2	5

III. Results and discussion

III.1. Respondents and focus of soil health

The total number of completed questionnaires was 13 (Figure 1, Annex II; Table A 1). The respondents were mainly active within single sector organisations where agricultural sector responses dominated (Figure 2). Three respondents stated multiple sector responsibilities. Other sectors that were mentioned were geomatics, coast guard, water quality, climate, atmosphere and mass movements, in addition to agriculture, forest and urban (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Distribution and number of answers per category of contacted organisation authority and company.

Figure 2. Number of respondents focusing on soil health per respective sector. Multiple choices were possible. Blue represents answers from respondents amongst authorities, red from research institutes and green from the private sector.

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The main focus areas of soil health were soil nutrients and land use change (7 and 7 respondents, respectively), while pollutants and acidification area the least in focus amongst the respondents (3 and 3 respondents, respectively) (Figure 3). Other variables mentioned for the focus within organisations were vegetation (tree) coverage in urban environment, blue economy (an economy based on, and actively beneficial for oceans) and capacity building amongst farmers.

Figure 3. Focus of soil health characteristics per business. Multiple choices were possible. Blue represents answers from respondents amongst authorities, red from research institutes and green from the private sector.

Few respondents answered questions regarding the use of remote sensing products within their organisations. Four indicated that they are currently using remote sensing products, while two did not currently use remote sensing products. Of these two, one respondent identified the potential to use remote sensing products in the future (in total, six responded). Goals mentioned for the use of remote sensing products were the follow-up of green space planning, the presence of and changes in urban nature, ensuring availability of up-to-date information regarding national maps, monitoring, and precision fertilisation of agricultural crops.

Of the six respondents that answered questions about the use of remote sensing products, three responded that their organisations use optical sensors (such as VIS, NIR and SWIR), while one organisation in addition uses thermal infrared sensors, microwaves, hyperspectral sensors, LiDAR and InSAR. Of these three respondents, there were no unified responses of which national data publishers (sources) that were used.

III.2. Opportunities and challenges with using remote sensing for soil health monitoring

Overall, the responses indicated an opportunistic view of the potential of using remote sensing data within the responding organisations and for monitoring soil health. The number of answers regarding challenges and potential for improvement in using remote sensing for soil health monitoring was fewer (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Number of respondents responding to questions regarding opportunities, improvement potential and challenges respectively, of using remote sensing for soil health monitoring

III.3. Skills, training, information and communication

In half of the respondents’ organisations, it was stated that expertise and knowledge for modelling and use of satellite data existed. There was an indicated need for additional competence for processing and analysis of data. Two respondents indicated that there was good knowledge within the organisation, but still a need for increased competence overall. There was also an indication from authorities and the private sector that the use of remote sensing data could be enhanced by increased training and cooperation between producers/distributors and users. This can be interpreted as that the knowledge of remote sensing data and processing is higher closer to the data production source organisation (actor) and needs to be extended to include users (Figure 5).

Open question commentary (Annex I; Question 4.1) brought up the importance of including communication with landowners (e.g., farmers). The comment concluded that these discussions can potentially be more important than simply increasing data sampling and presentation, as one of the challenging barriers to increase sustainable land use is individual behavioural change. Using soil health as a unifying umbrella concept can potentially help facilitate more of these discussions

Figure 5. Possibilities, improvement opportunities and challenges concerning skills, training and communication of using and sharing remote sensing data and developed products from remote sensing data. Blue represents answers from respondents amongst authorities, red from research institutes and green from the private sector.

III.4. Accessibility of data and the need to harmonise data processing

There was an agreement across respondents from multiple sectors that there is an opportunity to combine data from the national environmental monitoring programmes in Sweden (for forest (Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, 2023) and agricultural soils (Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet, 2022)) with remote sensing and that remote sensing data can be an advantage for continuous and long-term monitoring (Figure 5). Currently soil parameters in Sweden are included in the Swedish national environmental monitoring programme for soils. Examples of respondents comments included (Annex I; Question 4.8 - 4.9) there were consensus that the current national information based on environmental monitoring was preferred over European soil health information presented by the EU Soil Observatory. Furthermore, there was also agreement among these three respondents that indicators from remote sensing products cannot substitute the national environmental monitoring which is ground based observations /sampling. While fewer respondents, data from field campaigns have the potential to be more integrated in the analysis and validation of remote sensing data. Though remote sensing has the potential to be combined with ground-based observations from national monitoring to provide

continuous spatial and temporal information.

In addition, harmonised methods for data validation and quantification/presentation of errors within products was identified as important need to improve, as well as standards to present these errors, to ensure sufficient data quality and avoid overconfidence in data. With one less respondent (n = 4 respondents), there was indication that also platforms for data representation and distribution need to be standardized (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Possibilities, improvement opportunities and challenges concerning data accessibilities and data harmonisation. Multiple answers were possible. Blue represents answers from respondents amongst authorities, red from research institutes and green from the private sector.

III.5. Limitations of available technologies and knowledge; the need for further research

Remote sensing data was acknowledged to enable sampling of more soil variables due to ongoing development and increased availability of different sensors. Furthermore, it was recognised that remote sensing enables sampling of soil data over larger resolution at both spatial and temporal scales, as well as enable more cost-effective solutions. A few respondents (n = 3) recognised the potential of remote sensing products to support the analysis of soil health indicators by either the potential of development to detect conditions in deeper soil layers (made possible either through passive gamma ray spectrometry or by combining models of the land-vegetation-atmosphere system with ground-based and remote sensing observations) or by remote sensing enabling new methods and tools beyond those currently used

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in monitoring. Two respondents indicated that they find it difficult to see how remote sensing can be used for soil health monitoring within their operations (*Figure 7*).

In addition to the above response alternatives, more difficult challenges concerning the use of remote sensing products for monitoring soil health were added, i.e. detecting hidden objects in e.g. forest environment, detecting qualitative deviance, and integrate remote sensing data from different resources. In addition, reduced data quality due to cloud coverage was mentioned as a challenge, as well as that today there does not exist a way to quantify the carbon stock in soils through remote sensing.

Figure 7. Possibilities, improvement opportunities and challenges concerning available technologies of remote sensing solutions as well as further processing and storage capacities. Multiple answers were possible.

* Owner of data; dissemination of information about how data can be used; handling and collection of data that concern individual persons such as data at farm level; approval of individuals on how data may be used if personal data, equal access to data through open access

IV. Conclusion

Overall, the response rate among the contacted individuals was limited, which may partly be due to the questionnaire format lacking an initial opportunity for direct interaction between respondents and the survey administrator. Hence, this may have given the impression of less obligation or significance to reply, even though the emails sent out were personalized to each respondent. In addition, some respondents mentioned that while soil health is indeed of interest to their business/organisation operations, soil (land) health was not always at the core of projects where they are an active part. In other cases, the respondent referred back to respondents from other contacted organisations to have better knowledge to answer the questionnaire.

The results showed that there is an overall positive view for remote sensing data and its applications in monitoring soil health with potential for improved resolution. Furthermore, there is a view that remote sensing for soil health has potential to improve resolution, and as a potential complement to national soil monitoring data to assess soil health. Though current capacity of remote sensing to enhance soil health monitoring is still seen as limited. To improve the use of remote sensing, collaboration, communication and training opportunities between data providers, research and end users are needed to be continuously facilitated. One freestanding response to the aim of the questionnaire brought forward that there are private companies already offering solutions for monitoring of soil health and the potential to integrate these tools into research and government work may be limited by absence of communication, collaboration and clear guidelines regarding the use of and development of commercialised products between institutions. In addition, there was an identified need for platforms for data access to be harmonised, as well as for methods for validation and quantification of errors and uncertainties to be coordinated.

The cost of data collection, analysis, processing and access is seen as both a potential and a challenge to solve, and the long-term funding can be an obstacle. While this remains a challenge, the responses presented within this report did not reveal major suggestions on how long-term funding for monitoring soil health through remote sensing can be achieved. The only suggestion was the possibility to fund data collection by purchasing data for individual projects.

V. Authorship contribution

L. Malmquist: Methodology, writing – original draft, formal analysis, visualisation

J. Barron: Conceptualization, methodology, supervision, project administration, writing – review and editing, funding acquisition

J. Wetterlind: Conceptualization

References

- Renault, P., Xie, G., Weiss, M., 2024. *Technical feasibility in using CLMS satellite-based EO to estimate soil health indicators* (Draft). European Union.
- Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet, 2022. *Mark- och grödoinventeringen* [WWW Document]. SLU.SE. URL <https://www.slu.se/institutioner/mark-miljo/miljoanalys/akermarksinventeringen/undersokningar/mark-grodoinventeringen/> (accessed 6.10.21).
- Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, 2023. *About the Swedish Forest Soil Inventory* [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.slu.se/en/Collaborative-Centres-and-Projects/Swedish-Forest-Soil-Inventory/about-swedish-forest-soil-inventory/> (accessed 8.16.22).

Annexes

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Annex I:

Questionnaire

Below are the questions (in Swedish) sent out to the respondents.

Frågeformulär för undersökning av nuvarande och framtida behov av övervakning av markhälsoindikatorer med hjälp av fjärranalys

Denna undersökning vänder sig till experter inom markhälsa (framförallt inom skog, jordbruk) som använder eller kan tänkas använda fjärranalys i sin verksamhet. Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU) är ansvarig för denna undersökning inom projektet ["PREPSOIL: Preparing the EU Mission for healthy soils"](#). Fjärranalys innebär spårning och övervakning av ett områdes fysiska karakteristik genom att mäta reflekterade och utsänd strålning på avstånd, vanligtvis från satelliter eller flygplan.

Frågeformuläret syftar till att

1. Identifiera möjligheter och utmaningar (vetenskapliga, tekniska, kompetensbehov...) för att främja användning av fjärranalys för att stärka markhälsa
2. Föreslå åtgärder för att minimera eventuella utmaningar med att använda fjärranalys (vetenskapliga, tekniska, kompetensbehov...) samt andra utmaningar för Horisont Europas fortsatta arbete med markhälsa inom En giv för den europeiska marken ([EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe](#))

Undersökningen består av 5 delar, och tar ca 20–30 minuter att

besvara Stort tack för er hjälp

Kontakt: Louise Malmquist, louise.malmquist@slu.se

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1. Villkor och samtycke

Vi behöver ert samtycke för att kunna behandla information och eventuell personlig information i denna undersökning. Anonymiserade, sammanställda svar kommer delas i rapportform enbart innehållande organisation/myndighet och/eller tjänstetitel. Inga personuppgifter kommer delas utöver berörda personer inom WP5 PREPSOIL vid SLU. Se mer information i [bifogad länk](#).

Jag samtycker till att delta i denna enkät och till att SLU behandlar personuppgifter om mig på det sätt som förklaras i [bifogat dokument](#) om hantering av personuppgifter, inklusive känsliga uppgifter om jag lämnar sådana

2. Kontaktuppgifter till respondent

2.1. Företag/Organisation/Myndighet (obl.)

2.2. Tjänstetitel (obl.)

2.3. Efternamn, Förnamn

2.4. Mailadress

3. Indikatorer och produkter/service med fjärranalys (9 frågor)

3.1. Vilken huvudsaklig sektor arbetar er verksamhet inom? (fler svar är möjliga)

- Jordbruk
- Skogsbruk
- Urban
- Annat

Annat (v.v. specificera)

3.2. Vilken karaktäristik för markhälsa fokuserar er verksamhet på? (fler svar är möjliga)

- Markmekanisk karaktäristik (markpackning, erosion, markfukt, textur, mineraltyper...)
- Markemissioner (organiskt kol, mullhalt, växthusgaser...)
- Näringsämnen (mineralkväve, fosforinnehåll, mikronäringsämnen, C:N-kvot...)
- Förorenande ämnen (tungmetaller, organiska förorenande ämnen)
- Försurning (pH)
- Förändrad markanvändning (ändrad vegetation och markanvändning såsom hårdgörning av ytor, expansion av urbana områden eller infrastruktur, naturskyddsområden, skapande av naturbaserade lösningar för markanvändning...)
- Biologisk mångfald i mark och/eller vegetation (mikro, meso, makrofauna)
- Andra indikatorer/variabler

Andra indikatorer/variabler (v.v. specificera)

3.3. Hur använder ni markhälsoindikatorer- eller markanvändningsinformation? (fler svar är möjliga)

- Som input för vidare bearbetning inom er verksamhet
- Som bearbetade produkter och information till verksamhetens avvärmare
- Annat (v.v. specificera)

Annat (v.v. specificera)

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3.4. Använder ni någon typ av fjärranalysverktyg/produkter inom er verksamhet idag?

- Ja
- Nej, med det är något vi skulle vilja göra framöver
- Nej

3.5. Vilket/vilka är era mål med att använda fjärranalys för att undersöka markhälsa (markindikatorer) inom er verksamhet?

3.6. Vilken typ av fjärranalysverktyg/produkter använder ni er av inom er verksamhet?

a. Specificerad plattform/satelliter (fler val är möjliga)

- UAV
- Flygburna sensorer/flygbilder
- Plejaderna
- Sentinel
- ALOS-2
- GRACE
- Landsat
- SMAP
- EnMap
- Dove (Planet Labs)
- Andra

Andra (v.v. specificera)

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b. Sensorer (fler svar är möjliga)

- Optiska sensorer (t.ex. VIS, NIR, SWIR)
- Termisk infraröda sensorer
- Mikrovågor
- Hyperspektrala sensorer
- LiDAR
- InSAR
- Gravimetriska sensorer
- Gamma
- Andra

Andra (v.v. specificera)

c. Utgivare och bearbetade produkter (fler svar är möjliga)

- Dataväxt
- Jordbruksverket
- Länsstyrelserna
- Lantmännen
- Lantmäteriet
- Naturvårdsverket
- Planet variabler
- Skogsstyrelsen
- SLU
- Vultus
- Yara
- SGU
- Annan utgivare

Annan utgivare (v.v. specificera)

3.7. Vilka specifika produkter använder ni från ovanstående förkryssade utgivare? (T.ex. digitala åkermarkskartan SLU; Skred, ras och erosion, SGU...)

4. Möjligheter och förbättringspotential föra att nyttja fjärranalys i arbetet med övervakning av markhälsa och markanvändning i Sverige (10 frågor)

4.1. Vilka möjligheter ser ni med fjärranalys för att bedöma markhälsa inom er verksamhet? (Välj en eller flera alternativ)

- Det finns god kompetens inom satellitdata och modellering för utökad användning
- Möjlighet till insamling av varierade data tack vare utveckling av olika sensorer och verktyg samt förbättring av upplösning (spatial/temporal)
- God möjlighet att kombinera data från nationella övervakningsprogram med data insamlad genom fjärranalys Fjärranalysprodukter möjliggör snabbare datainsamling över större och/eller svåråtkomliga områden
- Fjärranalysprodukter möjliggör lättare kontinuerlig övervakning över tid
- Fjärranalys möjliggör detektion/mätning av markhälsoindikatorer som är mer kostnadseffektiva lösningar i jämförelse med fältarbete
- Jag har svårt att se hur fjärranalys ska kunna användas för bedömning av markhälsa inom min verksamhet

Annat

Annat (v.v. specificera)

4.2. Vilken förbättringspotential finns för att använda fjärranalys i bedömningen av markhälsa? (välj en eller flera alternativ)

- Fjärranalysprodukter med detektering av djupare jordlager än matjorden kan gynna analyser av markhälsoindikatorer
- Kostnaden för att tillgå (från databaser) data och/eller inhämta och bearbeta rådata kan vara hög för hårdvara, mjukvara och lagring
Data från fältkampanjer och fjärranalys data har potential att integreras bättre för validering, utvecklade analyser, fastställa samband mellan proxy-indikatorer och markindikatorer
- Utveckling av nya metoder/verktyg har potential för analys av markindikatorer som idag är svåra att mäta direkt
- Med främjad informationspridning, utbildning och samarbete mellan aktörer samt mellan distributör och användare av rådata och bearbetade data om hur data kan analyseras, användas och integreras med mätningar i fält kan fjärranalysdata nå större potential och konkurrens/dubbelarbete kan undvikas
- Ett nätverk/harmoniserade metoder för validering och korrigerig av mätfel/kvalitetsfel av fjärranalysdata behövs för att undvika övertro på förmågan hos fjärranalysprodukter att lösa problem/frågeställningar samt för att verifiera god datakvalitet
- Det finns ett behov av standardiserad utformning och introduktion av kommersiella (open access) plattformar för datatillgänglighet

Annat (v.v. specificera)

Annat (v.v. specificera)

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4.3. Vilka utmaningar behöver lösas för mer effektivt användande av fjärranalys? (välj en eller flera alternativ)

- Samarbete, kommunikation och support mellan intressenter, företag, verksamheter och forskning behöver utvecklas för gemensam målsättning och standarder för datalagring och databearbetning samt för behov mellan praktisk användning och dataframtagning.
- En gemensam grund för etiska aspekter behöver utvecklas (ägare av data; informationsspridning om hur data kan användas; hantering och insamling av data som berör individuella personer så som data på gårdsnivå; godkännande av individer om hur data får användas om personlig data, jämlik tillgång till data genom open access)
- Kompetens behövs för hur data bearbetning, analys samt kombination med data från andra applikationer (både mellan fjärranalysprodukter och data insamlad i fält)
- Behov av bearbetning (processorkraft), datalagring och backup behöver definieras och säkras för stora volymer data och säkras från yttre omständigheter så som systemfel.
- Harmoniserade metoder och redovisning för datakvalitet och bearbetning av mätfel för utvärdering av datas kapacitet till vidare analys
- Mer europeiskt/internationellt samarbete skulle kunna stärka vår nationella verksamhet (metoder, kompetens etc)
- Annat

Annat (v.v. specificera)

4.4. Ser ni specifika problem med fjärranalys som är svårare att lösa (t.ex. datakvalitet pga. molntäcke; svårighet att hitta barmark bland vegetation)?

- Nej
- Ja

Ja(v.v. specificera)

4.5. Ser ni speciella kompetens/kapacitetsbehov framöver internt för utökad användning av fjärranalys inom er verksamhet?

4.6. Ser ni speciella kompetens/kapacitetsbehov framöver bland avnämare/användare av er verksamhets produkter och service för utökad användning av fjärranalys inom er verksamhet?

4.7. Hur ser ni att framtagande av information och data med hjälp av fjärranalys ska finansieras långsiktigt?

4.8. Idag är svensk mark en del av det nationella miljöövervakningssystemet med [markprovtagning](#). Är denna information att föredra framför europeisk markhälsoinformation som presenteras av [EU Soil Observatory](#)?

- Ja
- Nej

4.9. Ser ni inom er verksamhet man kan ersätta den svenska markövervakningen med indikatorer från fjärranalys?

- Nej
- Ja

Om Ja, v.v. specificera vilken del av markövervakningen och hur/varför

4.10. Övriga kommentarer

5. Uppföljning av enkätresultat

5.1. Om vi önskar förtydligande till denna enkät, kan vi kontakta dig via telefon eller epost? (det tar inte mer än 30 min)

- Nej
- Ja

Om **Ja**, v.v. ange kontaktuppgift

5.2. Resultaten kommer att ingå i Projektet PREPSOILs rapport under 2025, vill du ta del av denna rapport?

- Nej
- Ja

Om **Ja**, v.v. ange kontaktuppgift

Tack för er medverkan!

Annex II:

Participating organisations

Table A 1. Organisations participating in the questionnaire per organisation category

Category	Authority/Organisation/Company	Website	
Authority	Lantmäteriet	Swedish Land Survey	https://www.lantmateriet.se/
	Rymdstyrelsen	Swedish National Space Agency	https://www.rymdstyrelsen.se/
	Naturvårdsverket	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/
	Jordbruksverket	Swedish Board of Agriculture	https://jordbruksverket.se/
	Länsstyrelsen Skåne län	County Administrative Board, Skåne County	https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/skane.html
	Länsstyrelsen Gotlands län	County Administrative Board, Gotland County	https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/gotland.html
Private sector	Hushållningssällskapet	The Household Society	https://hushallningssallsskapet.se/
	Dataväxt	DataVäxt	https://datavaxt.com/
	WSP	WSP	https://www.wsp.com/sv-se
Research institutes	Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	https://www.slu.se/